

ROLE OF NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020 IN STRENGTHENING THE EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS OF STUDENTS AT THE HIGHER EDUCATION LEVEL

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ABSTRACT

NEP 2020 in India marks a significant shift in education, aiming to develop overall and employability skills to meet 21st-century demands. It emphasises early childhood care and education to enhance cognitive, social, emotional, and physical abilities. The policy promotes a multidisciplinary approach, encouraging students to engage with multiple disciplines to foster creativity and critical thinking. NEP 2020 integrates theoretical and practical experiences to build employability skills in higher education students. It seeks to bridge the gap between industry and academia by promoting internships, apprenticeships, and industry interactions, enabling students to acquire skills aligned with industry needs for workplace adaptability. This research article analyses key elements of NEP 2020 to understand its impact on enhancing employability skills among degree-level students. The focus is on interpreting how NEP 2020 contributes to efficiently creating a skilled, industry-ready workforce. Implementing the NEP 2020 in education supports the Viksit Bharat 2047 vision, positioning India to achieve developed-country status by 2047.

Keywords: NEP 2020, Policy, Employability Skills, and Higher Education.

Introduction

The Union Cabinet of India launched the National Education Policy of India 2020 (NEP 2020) on July 29, 2020,

outlining the future goals for the country's educational system (Ministry of Human Resource Development, 2020). NEP 2020 is a comprehensive collection of policies

designed to transform the Indian education system. It is based on the following five guiding principles: accountability, affordability, quality, equity, and access. It will equip higher education students to address the many domestic and international issues of the present and future Santra & Basu, 2023). Making sure that no kid is denied the opportunity to pursue an education because of their origins or background is the main objective of NEP 2020. It strives to assist students in actively developing digital literacy to identify and revitalise their creative, analytical, problem-solving, and critical thinking skills Vodă et al., 2022). One of the primary objectives of this research article is to examine the critical aspects of the NEP 2020 policy and their potential impact on strengthening employability skills at the higher education level Maheshkumar S & Soundarapandian M, 2025). This bolsters graduates' employability, with a specific emphasis on cultivating skills that make

them more employable in a rapidly evolving job market. Therefore, the analysis provides an overview of the NEP 2020 and its significance in enhancing employability skills. The methodology is followed in an exploratory study. This research article attempts to analyse the employability of higher education graduates following the implementation of the New Education Policy 2020 in India (Bharat).

Features of Nep 2020 For Students

Instead of the current 10+2 education system, the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 proposes a new 5+3+3+4 framework. There are actually four phases to the structure: the foundational stage (for children ages 3–8), the preparation stage (for students in grades 3-5), the intermediate stage (for students in grades 6–8), and the secondary stage (for students in grades 9–12)(SALIENT FEATURES OF NEP 2020: HIGHER EDUCATION, n.d.).

Figure 1 - Source: Compiled by Author.

In India (Bharat), the NEP 2020 suggests reforms in higher education. The undergraduate curriculum spans three to four years, with several ways to graduate during that time. It will also include the necessary certifications: a certificate after a year of study in a field that includes professional and vocational areas; a diploma after two years of study; a degree after three years of study; or an undergraduate degree. The 4-year interdisciplinary undergraduate degree will be the recommended choice as it gives students the chance to experience all aspects of holistic and multidisciplinary education while also concentrating on their selected majors and minors (SALIENT FEATURES OF NEP 2020: HIGHER EDUCATION, n.d.).

Higher Education on Nep 2020

NEP 2020 provides insightful analysis and helpful suggestions on a range of topics related to higher education, such as the shift to multidisciplinary and holistic education, institutional autonomy, the creation of the National Research Foundation to support high-quality research, continuous professional development for teachers, technology integration, internationalisation of higher education, restructuring of the regulatory and governance architecture, interdisciplinary curricula, motivating blended pedagogy, valid, reliable, and blended assessment, and the accessibility

of content in Indian languages (Ministry of Human Resource Development, 2020). These are the new NEP 2020 policies to develop higher education in India (Bharat): a holistic approach and multidisciplinary to Education, Internationalisation and Distance Learning/Open Learning, Digitalization of Teaching-Learning Process, Research and Innovation, Skill Development and Vocational Education, and Enhance GER to 50% by the year 2035 (Maheshkumar S & Soundarapandian M, 2023).

i. Nep 2020: A Holistic Approach & Multidisciplinary to Education

The key features of the NEP 2020 contribute to a holistic education approach. That focus on multidisciplinary education, flexibility in course structures, and the integration of vocational skills are examined as crucial components in preparing students for the diverse demands of the job market and in-depth analysis of the key provisions of the NEP 2020 relevant to the higher educational level students, including changes in curriculum structure, flexibility in course choices, emphasis on multidisciplinary education, and the integration of vocational training (Makki et al., 2022). The National Education Policy of 1968 established the three-language formula, which mandates that, in addition to Hindi and English, modern Indian languages shall be taught in schools in Hindi-speaking regions. i.e., one native

language of India, one regional language, and one English language are defined as the language modules under the NEP 2020 Language Policy (SALIENT FEATURES OF NEP 2020: HIGHER EDUCATION, n.d.).

Figure 2

Source: Compiled by Author

ii. Internationalisation

Internationalisation is to be advanced by the NEP 2020 policy through faculty exchanges, collaboration with foreign universities, and recruitment of international students. The policy additionally provides for the establishment of a National Education Exchange Programme (NEEP) to promote educational interactions across nations. The initial proposal for foreign universities and transnational education (TNE) under the NEP 2020 aimed to provide the top 100 universities in the world access to India (Bharat). The establishment of franchises, verified online articulation and advancement programs, and transnational education (TNE) should all become increasingly widespread. Collaborations

between TNEs can significantly affect sustainability and nearby communities. Because it increases employability and competitiveness on a large scale, it may also directly impact economic growth. In addition, students benefit from a globally recognised degree that is less expensive than pursuing it elsewhere Marangell & D'Orazzi, 2023).

iii. Digitalisation of the Teaching-Learning Process

The NEP 2020 emphasises integrating technology into education to prepare students for the digital age and enhance employability skills, including coding, data analysis, and virtual collaboration. NEP 2020 encourages students to select an academic route that leads to the awarding of a certificate, diploma, or degree, paving the way for flexible and lifelong learning. Therefore, the cornerstone of the new National Education Policy 2020 in higher education is the Multiple Entry and Exit System (MEES)(Soni, 2023). This gives students the option to discontinue their course and resume it later, whenever they feel motivated to do so. Additionally, this is consistent with the NEP 2020 Academic Bank of Credits, which seeks to maintain a record of acquired qualifications in a government-authorised database Maheshkumar S & Soundarapandian M, 2024a). A major overhaul intended to improve the equity and student-friendliness

of the Indian higher education system is the Multiple Entry and Exit System (MEES). The well-planned implementation of this revolutionary step would guarantee learners zero-year loss and provide them with the freedom to learn at any time and from any location (Lata Narayan, 2021).

iv. Research and Innovation

The NEP 2020 plans to make India (Bharat) a global innovation and research hub by encouraging institutions to prioritise research and invest more in science and technology. This would be accomplished by encouraging interdisciplinary research and collaboration between institutions, industries, and academia. Meanwhile, the importance of creating a supportive environment for entrepreneurship and start-ups would also be emphasised to foster a culture of innovation and creativity in the country. Together with the IIMs and IITs, the government plans to establish Multidisciplinary Education and Research Universities (MERUs), which would pursue globalised educational norms (Lakshmi & Ugandhar, 2023). To stimulate research and development, a National Research Foundation would also be established. The National Research Foundation would financially support and assist with research projects across all disciplines, facilitating inter-institutional collaboration and encouraging landmark research achievements. The goal of this project would be to improve India's global image as

a leader in innovation and thus enhance the overall economy. The NEP 2020 also emphasises the importance of promoting global collaboration and partnerships, enabling knowledge sharing and cross-cultural learning experiences for students and researchers.

v. Vocational Education and Skill Development

The NEP 2020 recognises the critical importance of vocational education and skill development in preparing students to join the workforce. It suggests integrating work-integrated education and apprenticeships into conventional education to train students and equip them with skills. It promotes vocational education at all levels by incorporating trainee options into schools and colleges. This requires collaborating with industries to provide students with the necessary exposure. Emphasis on vocational education in the NEP 2020 will help bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and its practical application, enabling students to succeed in their chosen profession (Argheese, 2023). This will be implemented through internships, apprenticeships, and practical training in employability skills such as critical thinking and problem-solving. This will help students apply theoretical knowledge in practical work environments to develop the necessary skills. Critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, and communication are essential skills in

an ever-changing profession, leading to job satisfaction and personal development by enabling effective adaptation to new tasks and meeting employers' expectations (Maheshkumar S & Soundarapandian M, 2024b).

vi. Enhance Ger to 50% By the Year 2035

To improve the Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in higher education, it is intended to raise it to 50% from 26.3%, focusing on a multidisciplinary approach. The intended outcome is to develop individuals with 21st-century skills across the humanities, sciences, and technical fields, with the prospect of adopting this approach for all undergraduate courses offered in Indian universities.

Year	University	Colleges
2016-2017	846	40,026
2017-2018	903	39,050
2018-2019	993	39,931
2019-2020	1043	42,343
2020-2021	1113	43,796

Table 1: List of Year-Wise Universities and Colleges From 2016-17 To 2020-21.

Source: AISHE annual report 2022-2023

From Table 1, it can be seen that over the five years from 2016-17 to 2020-21, there is a steadily increasing trend in the number of universities and colleges. During 2016-17, the total number of colleges and universities recorded was the lowest. It gradually increased to 1,113 universities and 43,796 colleges in 2020-21. The AISHE 2022-23 annual report can be

considered an authentic source for this positive trend in higher education.

Year	Male	Female	Total
2016-2017	22.5	18.4	40.9
2017-2018	23.4	16.9	20.3
2018-2019	22.2	17.5	39.7
2019-2020	23.8	19.1	42.9
2020-2021	24.8	20.9	45.7

Table 2: Enrolment in Distance Education Between the Years 2016-17 and 2020-21.

Source: AISHE annual report 2022-2023

Note: Values in per cent.

The total enrolment data for Distance Education from 2016-17 to 2020-21, presented in Table 2 above, shows sustained growth each year. Total enrolment in 2016-2017 was 40.9 per cent, comprising 22.5 per cent male and 18.4 per cent female student enrolments. In 2020-2021, there was a sustained increase, with overall enrolment of 45.7 per cent, comprising 24.8 per cent and 20.9 per cent enrolment for male and female students, respectively. The AISHE 2022-2023 annual report is used to validate the increasing popularity of distance education among male and female students during the period.

Year	Enrolment(cr)
2016-2017	3.57
2017-2018	3.66
2018-2019	3.74
2019-2020	3.85
2020-2021	4.14

Table 3: Enrolment Between the Years 2016-17 And 2020-21 (In Crore).

Source: AISHE annual report 2022-2023

Table 3 indicates a steady increase in enrolment figures over the five years from 2016-17 to 2020-21, measured in crores. In 2016-2017, enrolment was 3.57 crores, with subsequent years witnessing consistent growth: 3.74 crores in 2018-2019 and 4.14 crores in 2020-2021. The AISHE annual report for 2022-2023 serves as the source, underscoring the escalating trend in overall enrolment in higher education during this period.

In 2035, the objective is to raise the Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) for higher education, including vocational education, from 26.3% (2018) to 50%. (Ministry of Education, 2021) A thorough and multidisciplinary education will help to create well-rounded individuals with essential 21st-century skills in a range of subjects, such as the humanities, sciences, social sciences, and professional, technical, and vocational domains of social engagement as an ethic, soft skills, such as communication, debate, and discussion and rigorous specialisation in one or more chosen fields. Eventually, this all-encompassing approach to education should be used in all undergraduate programs, including those in professional, technical, and vocational subjects. Raising the threshold for interdisciplinary education in India is the aim of the planned creation of research institutions and interdisciplinary education programs.

Challenges and Opportunities

While the NEP 2020 presents a promising framework, it has not been effectively implemented in India (Bharat). Higher education students will face these challenges, and these opportunities help them overcome them Santra & Basu, 2023). It discusses potential obstacles, such as infrastructure, faculty training, and stakeholder collaboration, while also highlighting opportunities to overcome them.

i. Skill Mismatch

The main challenge in skill mismatch is the gap between the skills acquired during higher education and the skills demanded by employers, which can reduce graduates' employability and opportunities. Curriculum reviews and industry consultations can ensure that educational programs align with current market needs, enhancing graduates' job-readiness.

ii. Limited Practical Exposure

Insufficient hands-on experience and practical exposure during the academic years may prevent students from applying theoretical knowledge in real-world scenarios, and integrating internships, apprenticeships, and practical training into the curriculum can provide students with valuable industry experience.

iii. Lack of Soft Skills

Employability is not only about technical skills; soft skills such as communication, teamwork, and critical thinking are equally

important and may be missing in graduates. Including soft skills development in the course can increase students' overall employability.

iv. Limited Industry Collaboration

A lack of cooperation between institutions and industry might lead to a mismatch between what is taught in academic institutions and what is required in industry. Industry contacts for collaborations or mentorship can help bridge these gaps and equip students with relevant industry skills and knowledge.

v. Lack of Entrepreneurial Skills

The conventional approach to employment might eclipse the nurturing aspect of entrepreneurial skills, and the ability to create opportunities for oneself and the chance to offer entrepreneurship courses, incubators, and resources for start-up development might cultivate an innovation and self-employment culture.

vi. Technological Advancements Outpacing Education

The risk of technological changes making old skills irrelevant may make it difficult for graduates to keep up with the changing demands of the job market, but incorporating the concept of learning, staying current with industry trends, and adopting new technologies into the learning process can address this problem.

vii. Inadequate Career Guidance

Students may lack appropriate guidance on career options and the skills

required, leading them to make uninformed decisions. The opportunity to implement career counselling and mentor initiatives can assist the students in making informed career choices.

viii. Regional Disparities

Job opportunities and skill needs could remain diverse across regions, leading to gaps in employability and the ability to customise education initiatives to each region. Decentralising skill development initiatives can overcome this.

ix. Inadequate Assessment Methods

Traditional assessment tools may also fail to assess skill sets, creativity, and problem-solving capabilities, which may affect the employability assessment process and the possibility of using different tools that involve different projects, presentations, and simulations.

x. Resistance to Change

A lack of resistance to implementing new or innovative teaching approaches may impede the embedding of employability-led approaches. Still, faculty development activities, workshops, and motivation for innovation may foster a more responsive higher education context.

Thus, capitalising on the opportunities presented would help create a higher education system that fully equips students for the employability needs of the modern work environment.

Conclusion

NEP 2020 for India (Bharat) provides a visionary roadmap for higher education to improve employability skills. There is a focus on interdisciplinary education, internationalisation, and digitalisation of education. It shows that 21st-century requirements inspire this document. To achieve the maximum benefits from NEP 2020, there is a strong need for interdisciplinary collaboration between academia and industry, novel teaching practices, and effective career counselling. If implemented, it could create a "dynamic and employable workforce that can make higher education relevant to contemporary requirements of professional worlds." By adopting the NEP 2020 in the education sector, "Viksit Bharat 2047" is being realised to make India a 'developed nation' by 2047.

Disclosure and Conflicts of Interest

The authors state that no financial, personal, or institutional conflicts of interest are found that might affect the design, conduct, analysis, or interpretation of the research presented in this paper. All the results are reported objectively and not influenced by external factors.

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